

Coaching Effectiveness in Ideation of PLN LDP Level 3

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ABSTRACT: This study evaluates the effectiveness of coaching in the Ideation of Leadership Development Program (LDP) Level 3 at PT. PLN (Persero), focusing on Coach-Client Relationship theories (Diller et al., 2022) and the ADKAR model by Hiatt (2006). It investigates the influence of coach-coachee dynamics, including Working Alliance – Task and Goal, Perceived Empathy, Perceived Need Supportive Behavior, and Closeness, on the success of the coaching process. Additionally, the research assesses the ADKAR model's components (Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, and Reinforcement) and Team Effectiveness based on Process Criteria (Effort-Related, Strategy-Related, and Knowledge & Skill-Related) in group project facilitation. Utilizing a quantitative approach, online questionnaires were distributed to 19 individuals who met the necessary criteria, including being participants in two coaching sessions of Ideation 3 Batch 5 and holding positions as potential leaders three tiers beneath the board of directors, consisting of Managers in Service Units, Vice Presidents in subsidiaries, and Assistant Vice Presidents. The responses then would be analyzed via IBM SPSS 27.0. Results indicate significant correlations between Coach-Client Relationship, ADKAR model, and Team Effectiveness, enhancing the understanding of coaching in personnel development. This finding highlights the necessity of a well-aligned coaching process to foster effective individual change readiness. Moreover, the finding also reveals that the coaching process extends beyond individual development and has a significant influence on team collaboration and effectiveness. A well-aligned coaching process can more effectively prepare individuals for the transitions and developments required in leadership roles and equip them to contribute positively to team environments. While this study contributes to a better understanding of coaching as a method for people development, there are some limitations concerning the sample and limited time of the study. Future research with a larger and varied sample, across-case data collection, and various additional data is needed. Testing with before-after questionnaires, forum group discussions, and a mixed-method approach would be particularly interesting, including diverse leadership levels and genders.

KEYWORDS: ADKAR, coaching, coach-client relationship, evaluation, team effectiveness – process criteria.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the current VUCA (volatile, uncertain, complex, ambiguous) era, organizations confront significant change challenges, underscored by a 70% failure rate in organizational change programs as noted by Pearse (2017). This environment, intensified by disruptive trends like technological advancements and workforce dynamics (Baran et al., 2020), demands a leadership shift from micromanagement to adaptability and leveraging internal growth drivers. Leaders are crucial in balancing goal achievement and managing organizational turbulence, a perspective supported by Rosha et al. (2016).

To address these challenges, organizations are increasingly focusing on new knowledge, skills, and integrated thinking. The 70:20:10 model of learning, which combines formal training, social learning, and experiential learning, is essential, with coaching playing a central role in facilitating sustainable change (Johnson et al., 2018). PT.PLN Persero, an Indonesian electricity company striving to lead in Southeast Asia, exemplifies these principles. In response to post-Covid-19 VUCA challenges, PT.PLN Persero has implemented a comprehensive Leadership Development Program (LDP) through its Education and Training Center (Pusdiklat), with a focus on coaching approach in its Ideation program. This research assesses the effectiveness of coaching in developing potential BOD-3 (Board of Director) leaders, analysing participants from LDP 3 Batch 5, with limitations such as participant number and time constraints. The effectiveness is measured by understanding the association between coaching process (Coach-Client Relationship model), individual change management (ADKAR model), and perceived team effectiveness (Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria) within leadership development.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Coaching

Coaching, as defined by Whitmore (2009), is a process of unlocking a person's potential to maximize their performance, emphasizing learning over teaching. It is a human development process using structured interaction to achieve sustainable change for the coachee, also known as the client (Park et al., 2008). The executive coaching industry, experiencing substantial growth over thirty years, has transformed from handling toxic leadership behaviors to developing high-potential performers (Reid et al., 2019). This study focuses on skills and performance coaching (SPC), aiming to enhance abilities and competencies. SPC follows external criteria, positively impacting personal growth and performance within organizational settings (Grant, 2012; Theeboom et al., 2013).

In Ideation 3 program, Coaches will facilitate two aspects: the development of competencies and the creation of innovation for participants' work units as part of a group project. For competency development, the evaluation considers the emergence and alignment of competencies with job projections. Meanwhile, the group project focuses on small-scale advancements, assisting participants in applying knowledge within specific job roles.

B. Coach-Client Relationship

Coach-Client Relationship is defined as the relationship between coach and coachee (client) during a coaching session. The Coach-Client Relationship has been named as one of the central roles in terms of coaching success. The effectiveness of executive coaching heavily relies on the quality of the relationship between the coach and the client. Without a strong coach-client relationship, coaching may not reach its full potential (Diller et al., 2022). In the Ideation 3 program, this relationship model will serve as the basis for evaluating the effectiveness of coaching. Diller et al. (2022) identify five key components that contribute to a highly valid coach-client relationship: Working alliance - Goal, which is the shared agreement on coaching objectives; Working alliance - Task, the consensus on tasks or activities for goal achievement; Perceived Need Support Behavior, highlighting the coach's role in offering appreciation, trust, and comprehensive support to the coachee; Perceived Empathy, where the coach demonstrates an understanding and empathetic stance towards the coachee's situation; and Closeness, representing the bond beyond professional collaboration.

C. ADKAR

The ADKAR, which stands for Awareness, Desire, Knowledge, Ability, Reinforcement; is a framework functions as a structured paradigm for comprehending the dynamics of individual and organizational level change. The application of this model is now extended for businesses, government agencies and communities change implementation purposes. The ADKAR model emerges as a foundational framework underpinning the developmental process, in the pursuit of providing organizational leaders with the necessary skills and knowledge to navigate the transformative challenges in their roles. There are five elements of ADKAR for a change to be realized (Hiatt, 2006): Awareness, representing the understanding of why a change is happening, the potential consequences of not changing, and knowing both internal and external factors driving the need for change; Desire, which is the personal choice and willingness to actively support a change, affected by the nature of change, personal situations, and internal motivators, which differ among individuals; Knowledge representing the necessary information, training, and education to comprehend how to navigate and implement a change. This includes knowledge related to behavior, procedures, tools, systems, abilities, job responsibilities, and methods essential for the successful implementation of a change; Ability: Demonstrating the practical capability to implement a change successfully, translating acquired knowledge into action at the required performance levels; Reinforcement: The factors, both internal and external, contributing to the sustained success of a change. External reinforcements may involve recognition, rewards, and celebrations, while internal reinforcements could be personal satisfaction or other individual benefits resulting from the change. Facilitating meaning-making among employees is a crucial factor that needs to be prioritized by organizations and leaders in the initial stages of organizational change (Heuvel et al, 2013). Several prior studies confirm coaching as a valuable tool for enhancing awareness and intrinsic motivation, including goal significance (Cox et al., 2014). It has been shown to increase meaning (Phaekwamdee et al., 2022) and empower individuals, providing a clear understanding of objectives and the confidence to implement action plans. Coaching fosters employee responsibility, cultivating shared accountability and reinforcement (Fey et al., 2022).

Hypothesis 1 (H1). Coach-Client Relationship positively **associated** with ADKAR of Ideation 3 participants.

D. Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria

Team Effectiveness Criteria is an instrument to measure overall quality of team task process. It is a component of the Team Diagnostic Survey, an instrument designed to analyse the strengths and weaknesses of work teams and for researching team behaviour and

performance (Wageman, 2005). From three components of team effectiveness criteria (Wageman, 2005), process criteria are chosen as the most relevant criteria in the context of Coaching in Ideation 3 Batch 5. The process criteria is the combined effort of team members on the task, the effectiveness of strategies for team task performance, and how well the team utilizes the various range of member knowledge and skill (6 Team Conditions, 2022).

In measuring the quality of the team task process, the following three sub-scales are evaluated: Effort-related Criteria related to how participants collaborate to foster shared commitment to tasks and the team, observed through the level of effort they contribute to the assignments; Strategy-related Criteria related to the effectiveness of the team's performance approaches in creating a unique and innovative approach aligned with the tasks; and Knowledge & Skill-related Criteria, related to the extent to which the team optimally leverages the knowledge and skills of its members.

Hypothesis 2 (H2). Coach-Client Relationship positively associated with Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria

Hypothesis 3 (H3). ADKAR positively associated with Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

III. METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative methodology to investigate relevant variables. The specific research titled "Coaching Effectiveness in Ideation of PLN LDP Level 3" utilizes quantitative data collection methods, primarily through the use of structured questionnaires as the primary tool for survey research. The analysis focuses on 19 participants of Ideation 3, both male and female, that enrolled in coaching sessions of Leadership Development Program (LDP). The questionnaires consist of 64 items, employing a 5-point Likert Scale ranging from "Strongly Disagree" to "Strongly Agree", and index for measurement. The study applies an inter-correlation analysis using Pearson Correlation to assess the strength and direction of the relationship among the identified variables. The analysis includes using IBM SPSS 27.0 to perform descriptive statistics analysis, assess the validity and reliability of constructs, and determine significant influences among variables, followed by an inter-correlation analysis between the three aforementioned variables.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS

In this research, the initial stage involved analyzing the measurement model for reliability and validity using IBM SPSS 27.0 application. The data's reliability was confirmed by elevated Cronbach's Alpha figures, ranging from 0.821 to 0.988, which exceeded the usual threshold, thereby confirming the variables' reliability. In parallel, the validity of these variables was validated through Pearson Correlation and P-Value evaluations, indicating strong correlations in the range of 0.807 to 0.975. This high correlation not only validated the variables and their indicators but also affirmed their suitability for further analysis.

The overall mean values of the variables—Coach-Client Relationship, Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria, and ADKAR were categorized as high or very high, indicating a strong presence of collaboration, empathetic connection, and effective team processes among participants. However, the standard deviations across the dimensions of Coach-Client Relationship, ADKAR, and Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria reveals a complex picture. The Coach-Client Relationship dimensions demonstrated high mean scores, indicating strong perceived coaching relationships, and with relatively constant standard deviations, suggesting constant individual experiences and perceptions. Similarly, ADKAR components showed uniformly high mean values, reflecting positive reception towards change management processes, coupled with relatively lower standard deviations, indicating more consistent perceptions among participants. Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria dimensions also recorded high means, pointing to effective

team processes and collaborations, despite having lower mean scores when compared to other indicators. Specifically, indicators that are stated in negative statement scores lower. There are notable varied standard deviations in Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria, highlighting differences in individual experiences of team effectiveness.

A. Inter-Correlations on Each Variable

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics Result

Variable	Coach-Client Relationship	ADKAR	Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria
Coach-Client Relationship	-	-	-
ADKAR	.967**	-	-
Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria	.691**	.755**	-

**Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

*Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 2. Inter-Correlation of Each Dimensions

Sub-Scales	WAT	WAG	PNSB	PE	CL	AW	DS	KN	AB	RF	EF	ST	KS
WAT	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
WAG	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PNSB	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
PE	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AW	.932**	.850**	.970**	.888**	.941**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
DS	.750**	.525*	.744**	.757**	.778**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
KN	.854**	.854**	.745**	.875**	.822**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
AB	.861**	.894**	.767**	.829**	.830**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
RF	.936**	.890**	.924**	.870**	.920**	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
EF	.466*	.254	.355	.412	.507*	.373	.586**	.382	.437	.468*	-	-	-
ST	.728**	.620**	.625**	.604**	.715**	.740**	.435	.642**	.649**	.699**	-	-	-
KS	.733**	.727**	.594**	.721**	.718**	.629**	.527*	.821**	.833**	.646**	-	-	-

This study utilizes Pearson Correlation to assess the interrelationships among the Coach-Client Relationship, ADKAR, and Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria variables, categorizing correlations as weak (0.1 to 0.3), moderate (0.3 to 0.5), and strong (0.5 to 1.0). Key findings include a significant overall correlation of 0.967** between Coach-Client Relationship and ADKAR, highlighting a strong link that supports the hypothesis of a positive correlation between effective coaching and successful change management (**Hypothesis 1**). Additionally, a strong correlation of 0.691** correlation between Coach-Client Relationship and Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria (**Hypothesis 2**), and a notable 0.755** between ADKAR and Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria (**Hypothesis 3**) further prove their association. The findings prove that **Hypothesis 1**, **Hypothesis 2**, and **Hypothesis 3** are valid. Specific results show the highest correlation of 0.970** between Perceived Need Supportive Behavior (PNSB) and Awareness (AW), followed by Closeness (CL) and Awareness (AW) with correlation of 0.941*, underscoring the impact of coaching on change awareness. There are also significant correlations of both Closeness (CL) and Working Alliance – Task (WAT) with Awareness

(AW), emphasizing the importance of proximity outside of working alliance and task agreement in change sustainability. All of the dimensions of Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria are associated with Coach-Client Relationship's, except for effort dimension which only correlates with Working Alliance – Task (WAT) and Closeness (CL). In terms of team dynamics, Effort-Related Criteria (EF) correlate with Desire (DS) and Reinforcement (RF), linking team effort to members' willingness to support change and coach's support, while Strategy-Related Criteria (ST) strongly correlate with Awareness (AW), pointing to the role of change awareness in strategic team performance. Knowledge (KN), Ability (AB), and Reinforcement (RF)'s correlations with Strategy (ST), although lower, highlight their relevance in strategic efficacy. Moreover, Knowledge & Skill-Related Criteria (KS) show strong correlations with all ADKAR dimensions. The study concludes that the interconnectedness of coaching, change management, and team effectiveness is empirically supported, with the detailed correlation analysis offering valuable insights into how different aspects of coaching and change management influence team dynamics and effectiveness.

Strong Positive Inter-Correlations

The study's results offer significant insights into the dynamics of the coaching process in Ideation 3's coaching sessions. Firstly, there are positive relationship between the Coach-Client Relationship and ADKAR dimensions, indicating that effective coaching relationships—characterized by task and goal alignment, empathy, closeness, and supportive behaviour—enhance participants' awareness, desire, knowledge, ability, and reinforcement in the change process. Secondly, correlations between the Coach-Client Relationship and Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria suggest that mutual agreement of task and strong coach-participant bonds, particularly the demonstration of closeness by the coach, are likely to increase participants' commitment and effort in group projects. A comprehensive demonstration of Coach-Client Relationship traits fosters innovative strategies, adaptability, and effective plan implementation in team settings. Additionally, such relationships encourage serious consideration of team members' ideas, knowledge sharing, and skilful learning from group project experiences. Lastly, the study finds that certain ADKAR sub-scales correlate with Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria. Individuals with a clear understanding of program goals, a willingness to participate, knowledge of how to change, the ability to apply learned knowledge, and receiving positive reinforcement are more inclined to contribute actively to team knowledge-sharing and skill development. The ability to innovate in team strategy is linked to these factors, except for the desire to participate. Moreover, a strong desire to be involved and receiving reinforcement from the coach significantly impacts team members' effort.

However, the significant intercorrelations observed in Table 1 and Table 2 may be attributed to similar underlying concepts among certain dimensions. For instance, WAT (Working Alliance - Task) and Ability (AB) both relate to task agreement and performance capabilities in change or coaching contexts. Similarly, Perceived Empathy (PE) and Desire (DS) share a common thread of requiring personal connection and understanding, despite focusing on empathy and personal motivation, respectively. Furthermore, Perceived Need Supportive Behaviour (PNSB) and Reinforcement (RF) are both concerned with supportive actions that encourage sustained behaviour or change.

Despite these overlaps, the dimensions from the Coach-Client Relationship, the ADKAR model, and Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria derive from distinct theoretical foundations. The Coach-Client Relationship dimensions emphasize interpersonal dynamics within a coaching framework, whereas the ADKAR model is anchored in change management theory, outlining the stages of individual change. Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria are based on team dynamics theory, focusing on team operational effectiveness and collaboration. The interaction of these dimensions highlights their complementary roles across coaching, change management, and team dynamics. For example, high Perceived Empathy in coaching can enhance a coachee's Desire to engage in change. In practice, these dimensions serve unique functions: coaching sessions focus on building relationships and personal growth, change management initiatives aim to develop comprehensive change competencies, and team effectiveness endeavours enhance collaboration and strategic execution. Collectively, these dimensions contribute differently to organizational development and leadership.

Low to Moderate Positive Inter-Correlations

There are several relatively weak relationship between each dimension. In the intercorrelation between ADKAR and Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria, the first result reveals that while awareness, knowledge, and ability are important, they are not a strong predictors of the effort team members will contribute. Second, a desire to be involved in change process is not a strong predictor related to how effectively a team plans and executes its strategies. Meanwhile, in the intercorrelation table between Coach-

Client Relationship and Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria, the specific aspects of the coaching relationship represented by Working Alliance - Goal (WAG), Perceived Need Supportive Behavior (PNSB) and Perceived Empathy (PE) might have a limited direct influence on the effort that team members contribute to tasks.

B. Discussion

The study suggests that rephrasing negative questionnaire items into positive formulations could enhance comprehension, as indicated by low mean values and high standard deviations in certain items of Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria. The Coach-Client Relationship is identified as crucial in Ideation 3, associated with individual competency and group project development. Coaches are advised to foster this relationship through active listening, empathy, trust, safety, and ethical practices, as outlined by ICF (2022), to create a supportive environment. Furthermore, coaching's positive impact on ADKAR dimensions and Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria aligns with the company's transformation strategy, highlighting the role of coaching in managing individual development during change processes. Incorporating ADKAR stages and collaborative projects could strengthen team dynamics and strategic execution.

Additionally, the initiative involving Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria offers a framework for coaches to aid participants in individual change management. However, further research is needed to explore the cause-and-effect relationship among Coach-Client Relationship, ADKAR model, and Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria. Specific indicators, particularly in the Closeness dimension of Coach-Client Relationship, scored below average, signalling the importance of coaches building deeper personal connections for coaching success. As Diller et al. (2022) emphasize, closeness is proven to be associated with coaching satisfaction, indicating a need for further research to understand the correlation between closeness and coaching satisfaction and success within Ideation 3's coaching context.

V. CONCLUSION

The findings reveal positive and strong relationships among Coach-Client Relationship, ADKAR model for individual competency development, and Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria for group project quality in Ideation 3 coaching sessions. A well-aligned coaching process fosters effective individual change readiness and has a significant influence on team collaboration and effectiveness. This study contributes to a better understanding of coaching effectiveness in a Leadership Development Program. Future research should explore these variables in more diverse samples and different organizational levels, employing varied approaches and measurement methods. It is suggested to investigate the causal relationships using Linear Regression and consider factors like coach's coaching expertise and certification, external reinforcements like rewards, and internal factors like personal satisfaction. Mixed methods, such as 360-degree interviews and forum group discussions, are recommended for a comprehensive qualitative understanding. Additionally, the potential impact of a coach assistant on coaching effectiveness, particularly in relation to effort-related criteria, presents an avenue for future research to enhance coaching outcomes.

VII. LIMITATIONS

This study uses several theories, namely Coach-Client Relationship, the ADKAR model, and Team Effectiveness – Process Criteria, and examines the effectiveness of coaching process in facilitating individual change management and group dynamic effectiveness. The subjects in this study are participants of coaching in Ideation 3 Batch 5 on BOD-3 Levels. The author has limited access to the participants due to time constraints, which the research is conducted from September 2023 to January 2024, and primary data collection period within December 2023.

VI. APPENDIX

Table 3. Respondents' Profile

Gender	
Male	17
Female	2
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Age	
30-40 years old	10

40-50 years old	9
Work Experience	
10-20 years	17
≥ 20 years	2
Education	
Bachelor	16
Master's	3

Table 4. Questionnaire Items

1) Coach-Client Relationship (Adapted from Diller et al 2022, 25 items)

<i>Sub-Scales</i>	<i>Instruction</i>	<i>Adapted Statements</i>	<i>Item Code</i>	
Working alliance: Tasks	My coach and I...	Work together to set coaching goals.	WAT01	
		Work toward goals we mutually agree on.	WAT02	
		Mutually agree on what is important for me to work on	WAT03	
		Are in agreement about what competency development would be good for me.	WAT04	
Working alliance: Goals	Coaching helps me to...	Realize how I can develop my competency.	WAG01	
	-	Coaching provides me new ways of looking at my self-development related to my future job role.	WAG02	
	I believe that...	What I do in coaching will help me achieve the targeted competency development.	WAG03	
	-	The way we work on my problems is appropriate.	WAG04	
Perceived need supportive behavior	My coach...	Made me feel comfortable.	PNSB01	
		Made me feel in good hands.	PNSB02	
		Made me feel valued.	PNSB03	
		Made me feel like I could handle personal challenges.	PNSB04	
		Made me feel like I could achieve my goals.	PNSB05	
		Had confidence in my ability to do well.	PNSB06	
		Encouraged me to self-reflect.	PNSB07	
		Encouraged me to think for myself about how I might best proceed the Ideation stages.	PNSB08	
		Listened to me about how I would like to do individual contribution / activity and group project.	PNSB09	
		Always gave me the opportunity to make my own decisions.	PNSB10	
Perceived empathy	In my perspective, my coach often...	Take my perspective.	PE01	
		Feel with me.	PE02	
		Feel the same or similar emotions as me.	PE03	
Closeness	My coach...	-	I feel connected to my coach.	CL01
		-	Is very likable.	CL02
		-	Is very close to me.	CL03
		-	...and I are on the same wavelength.	CL04

2) ADKAR (Adapted from Kaichan et al 2018, 20 items)

Sub-Scales	Instruction	Adapted Statements	Item Code
Awareness	Coaching helps me to...	Understand the reasons for Ideation stages in the LDP program.	AW01
		Understand the difficulties in improving my individual competency.	AW02
		Know how effective Ideation stages in the LDP program is.	AW03
		Aware of the goals of Ideation stages in the LDP program.	AW04
Desire	Coaching makes me...	Feel excited to be part of Ideation stages in the LDP program.	DS01
		Believe this individual competency development plan will provide me a lot of opportunities.	DS02
		Support the implementation of Ideation stages in the LDP program.	DS03
		Believe I benefit from the individual competency development.	DS04
Knowledge	Coaching helps me to...	Have the required skills to adapt to my individual competency development plan.	KN01
		Understand how my work is related to individual competency development plan.	KN02
		Clarify what individual competency development should I implement.	KN03
		<i>*Note: This question is added by the author for specific need in coaching Ideation 3 context.</i>	
		Recall the previously acquired knowledge from the LDP modules and connect them to my individual competency development.	KN04
		<i>*Note: This question is added by the author for specific need in coaching Ideation 3 context.</i>	
Ability		Adapt in my competency development process.	AB01
		Positively contribute to individual activity and group project.	AB02
		Do better at work, due to the coaching sessions I attended.	AB03
		Have the ability to improve my competencies at a level that is needed for my role.	AB04
Reinforcement	My mentor / manager ...	My coach gives me the essential feedback to help me improve my individual development plan.	RF01
		<i>*Note: This question is added by the author for specific need in coaching Ideation 3 context.</i>	
		My mentor/manager supports this competency development process.	RF02
		<i>*Note: This question is added by the author for specific need in coaching Ideation 3 context.</i>	

-	Coach helps me resolve the uncertainty during Ideation stages in the LDP program.	RF03
-	I personally develop with this competency development.	RF04

3) Team Effectiveness - Process Criteria (Adapted from Wageman 2016, 9 items)

Sub-Scales	Instruction	Adapted Statements	Item Code
Effort-Related Criteria	Every member on this team...	Demonstrate their commitment to our team by putting in extra time and effort to help group project succeed.	EF01
		Is motivated to have the team succeed.	EF02
	-	Some members of our team do not carry their fair share of the overall group project workload. (R)	EF03
Strategy-Related Criteria	Our team...	Often comes up with innovative ways of proceeding with the work that turn out to be just what is needed.	ST01
		Often falls into mindless routines, without noticing any changes that may have occurred in our situation. (R)	ST02
		Has a great deal of difficulty actually carrying out the plans we make for how we will proceed with group project. (R)	ST03
Knowledge and Skill-Related Criteria	-	How seriously a member's ideas are taken by others on our team often depends more on who the person is than on how much he or she actually knows. (R)	KS01
	Every member on this team...	Members of our team actively share their special knowledge and expertise with one another.	KS02
	Our team...	Is quite skilled at capturing the lessons that can be learned from our group project experiences.	KS03

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